

Research Paper

Skills–Job Role Alignment and Organisational Productivity in the Oil and Gas Sector of Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the relationship between skills–job role alignment and organisational productivity in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State, with particular emphasis on the influence of soft skills development on workforce efficiency and innovation. The study was motivated by the persistent challenges of low productivity, skill mismatches, and inadequate manpower development practices observed within the industry. A mixed-method research design was adopted, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study population comprised 3,000 employees drawn from Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), Conoil Producing Limited, and Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO). Using Taro Yamane’s formula, a sample size of 400 respondents was selected through census and purposive sampling techniques. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, while descriptive statistics, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and thematic analysis were employed for data analysis using SPSS. The findings revealed that skills–job role alignment had a strong and significant positive relationship with organisational productivity and performance ($r = 0.788$, $p < 0.01$). The study further found that soft skills development significantly enhanced workforce efficiency and innovation ($r = 0.756$, $p < 0.01$). Interview responses corroborated the quantitative findings, indicating that proper employee placement, effective communication, teamwork, adaptability, and interpersonal competencies improved productivity, reduced operational errors, strengthened collaboration, and fostered innovation. The study concluded that manpower development remains a critical driver of sustainable organisational success in the oil and gas sector. It therefore recommended the adoption of competency-based workforce planning, effective skills–job alignment strategies, and continuous soft skills development programmes to improve organisational productivity and competitiveness.

Keywords: Skills–Job Role Alignment, Organisational Productivity, Soft Skills Development, Workforce Efficiency, Oil and Gas Sector.

I. Introduction

In today’s highly competitive and dynamic oil and gas industry, especially in resource-rich regions like Bayelsa State, Nigeria, the critical role of manpower development in enhancing organisational productivity cannot be overemphasised. However, despite the abundant human and natural resources available in the state, many oil and gas firms continue to grapple with low productivity, high operational inefficiencies, and underutilisation of local talents. This persistent gap raises serious concerns about the adequacy, quality, and implementation of manpower development strategies in the sector (Ogidi & Akujuru 2026). A major problem evident in many oil and gas firms is the inadequate investment in continuous employee training and capacity building. Many organisations in the sector often prioritise short-term operational goals over long-term human capital development, thereby neglecting the need for upskilling employees to meet evolving technological and industry demands (Ogbu & Adebayo, 2021). This failure to adequately train and retrain staff results in a workforce that lacks the required competencies, creativity, and motivation to drive innovation and high productivity (Ogidi et al. 2026a). Another critical challenge is the mismatch between employees’ skills and job roles. This situation often stems from poor workforce planning and

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ineffective talent management systems. As such, many employees are either overqualified or underqualified for their respective roles, leading to inefficiencies, reduced job satisfaction, and poor performance outcomes (Agbo & Ezeugwu, 2020). Furthermore, poor performance appraisal systems, limited career progression opportunities, and absence of structured development frameworks have continued to demoralise the workforce, leading to low commitment and high employee turnover rates in the industry. Additionally, there is an observable lack of emphasis on soft skills development such as leadership, communication, and problem-solving, which are crucial for organisational growth and employee effectiveness (Eleyi & Ogidi 2026). Many development initiatives remain too technical or theoretical, failing to equip staff with holistic competencies required for dynamic work environments (Chukwuemeka & Godwin, 2023). Compounding these challenges is the frequent reliance on expatriates due to perceived gaps in local expertise, thereby undercutting indigenous capacity building and raising questions of sustainability and inclusivity in manpower planning (Nwogu & Ogidi 2026). Despite numerous studies on employee training and productivity in Nigeria, there is a notable gap in empirical investigations focusing specifically on the oil and gas sector in Bayelsa State (Ogidi & Abdularahman 2025). Most existing literature fails to explore the link between manpower development and productivity within the context of localised industrial practices and socio-economic peculiarities of the region. This study, therefore, seeks to bridge this gap by examining the extent to which manpower development strategies influence productivity in selected oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State.

II. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine StateSkills–Job Role Alignment and Organisational Productivity in the Oil and Gas Sector of Bayelsa State. The specific objectives of the study are to;

1. Assess the relationship between skills-job role alignment and organisational productivity in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State.
2. Investigate the impact of soft skills development on workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms.

III. Research Questions

The following questions are constructed to critically evaluate the objectives of the study;

1. What is the relationship between skills-job role alignment and organisational productivity in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State?
2. How does soft skills development impact workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms?

IV. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses, which will be tested at a 0.05 significance level, are formulated to guide the study:

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between skills-job role alignment and organisational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between soft skills development and workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms.

V. Conceptual Review

Concept of Employee Productivity

Employee productivity is a crucial aspect of organisational success, serving as a primary measure of efficiency in a workplace environment. In the context of any business or industry, productivity refers to the amount of output produced per unit of input, which is typically time or resources. According to Lee (2019),

employee productivity is a critical determinant of an organisation's overall performance. It is essential to understand the dynamics between employee productivity and the factors influencing it, especially in industries where human capital is integral to success, such as the oil and gas sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria (Akujuru & Ogidi, 2025a). The concept of productivity can be traced back to classical economics, where productivity was simply viewed as the ratio of output to input. However, in the modern workforce, this concept has evolved. It now encompasses various dimensions, such as work quality, innovation, and efficiency. Employee productivity is no longer just about producing more in less time but also about enhancing the quality of work and fostering innovation (Aguinis, 2019). Moreover, the relationship between employee productivity and organisational success is widely discussed in literature, where scholars agree that higher productivity directly contributes to achieving organisational goals, increasing profitability, and maintaining competitive advantage (Kaplan & Norton, 1992). Employee productivity in industries like oil and gas is often linked to both tangible and intangible elements. Tangible elements include measurable outputs like the quantity of oil extracted, whereas intangible factors include employee engagement, satisfaction, and creativity in solving problems (Jones & Hooper, 2017). In oil and gas firms, employee productivity is critical due to the industry's high operational costs and the sophisticated technologies involved (Akujuru & Ogidi, 2025b). A more productive workforce is capable of operating more efficiently, maximising output while minimising waste and the risk of accidents (Cameron & Green, 2015).

Productivity in this context is not just a function of individual performance but is deeply influenced by the organisational structure, work environment, training opportunities, and management practices. A critical driver of employee productivity is effective training and development. According to Pradhan and Jena (2017), organisations that invest in the continuous development of their employees often experience higher productivity levels (Ogidi et al., 2024). This is particularly true for sectors like oil and gas, where the technical skills required are highly specialised, and continuous learning is essential to keep up with evolving technologies. The oil and gas industry in Bayelsa State provides an illustrative case of how employee productivity is intertwined with job satisfaction, skill enhancement, and organisational performance (Titity & Ogidi, 2024). Workers in this sector, especially those in upstream operations such as drilling and exploration, must be highly skilled to deal with the complexities of the job. They also face high-pressure environments where safety and efficiency are paramount (Ogidi, 2024a). As observed by Okeke (2020), employees who feel equipped to handle their tasks and who are provided with opportunities for career growth are more likely to be productive and engaged in their roles.

The Impact of Motivation on Employee Productivity

Motivation is another critical factor that influences employee productivity. Motivation drives employees to put forth their best effort and go beyond the basic requirements of their job. According to Herzberg's two-factor theory (1959), motivation is influenced by both hygiene factors (such as working conditions and salary) and motivators (such as recognition and career growth opportunities). When both factors are present in an organisation, employees are more likely to be productive. In the oil and gas sector, where the work environment can be physically demanding and hazardous, employees' motivation levels are essential for maintaining high productivity (Ogidi, 2024b). According to a study by Ogunyemi (2016), employees working in high-risk environments like the oil and gas sector often require a higher level of motivation to maintain performance under pressure. Workers who feel motivated by fair compensation, recognition, and career progression are more likely to remain focused and productive despite the challenging nature of their roles. Furthermore, motivation is intricately linked to employee engagement, which is another key driver of productivity. According to Saks (2006), engaged employees are more likely to be committed to their work, resulting in better performance. In Bayelsa State's oil and gas sector, where firms face competition for skilled workers, organisations that invest in employee motivation and engagement strategies are more likely to maintain a highly productive workforce. Motivated employees also exhibit greater problem-solving abilities and innovation, which are critical for improving efficiency and achieving organisational goals (Gilbert, 2016).

The Role of Organisational Culture in Employee Productivity

Organisational culture is a significant determinant of employee productivity. According to Deal and Kennedy (1982), a strong organisational culture creates a work environment where employees feel aligned with the company's values and goals, which leads to higher productivity. In the oil and gas sector, where the work is often complex and collaborative, a positive organisational culture can facilitate communication, teamwork, and effective problem-solving, all of which enhance productivity. A healthy organisational culture fosters a sense of belonging and motivates employees to contribute positively to the company's goals. In Bayelsa State, where oil and gas companies are often large and dispersed, promoting a strong organisational culture that emphasises safety, respect, and mutual support is critical for improving employee productivity (Amadi & Ogidi, 2023). Employees who feel that they are part of a team and that their contributions are valued are more likely to be engaged in their work and perform at higher levels (Boxall & Purcell, 2016). Moreover, a culture that prioritises continuous improvement and innovation can also drive productivity. According to Schein (2010), companies with cultures that encourage learning and development create environments where employees can thrive, ultimately leading to increased productivity. In the oil and gas sector, where technological advancements are continuous, fostering a culture of innovation ensures that employees are equipped to adapt to new challenges, leading to improved operational performance.

Concept of Employee Productivity

Employee productivity refers to the effectiveness with which employees perform their tasks in alignment with the goals and objectives of an organisation. It is a measure of output in relation to input and is crucial in determining an organisation's overall performance. Employee productivity plays a pivotal role in the oil and gas sector, where the demand for efficiency is constant and the cost of operational failures is high. The concept of employee productivity can be examined from various angles, with scholars offering differing perspectives on what constitutes productivity and how it should be measured. The traditional view of employee productivity focuses on the quantity of output produced within a specific timeframe. However, more recent interpretations of productivity consider the quality of the output as well as the impact of employee engagement, job satisfaction, and organisational culture (Jackson & Schuler, 2019). According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2018), productivity is not just about the number of tasks completed; it is about how well these tasks contribute to the strategic objectives of the organisation. This broader view highlights the importance of employee effectiveness and efficiency in driving organisational success. In the context of the oil and gas industry in Bayelsa State, employee productivity can be defined as the ability of workers to perform their tasks efficiently, safely, and in compliance with industry regulations while contributing to the overall success of the company. As oil and gas operations are highly complex and often dangerous, maintaining high levels of productivity is critical for ensuring that operations run smoothly and that safety standards are met (Olajide, 2021). Workers in this industry are often tasked with operating complex machinery, adhering to strict safety protocols, and dealing with volatile and high-risk environments, all of which demand a high level of skill and productivity. Employee productivity is traditionally assessed through performance metrics such as output per hour, efficiency rates, and the quality of work produced. However, several other factors, including motivation, employee satisfaction, skills development, and training, also contribute significantly to productivity levels. According to Armstrong (2014), employee productivity is not only a function of the tools and technologies available but also of the skills, attitudes, and behaviours of the employees themselves. A workforce that is motivated, adequately trained, and well-equipped to handle the challenges of their roles will naturally exhibit higher levels of productivity.

Several scholars have linked employee productivity to the development of human capital. According to Becker (1994), human capital refers to the skills, knowledge, and abilities that individuals possess and can be leveraged to enhance productivity. Investment in human capital, through training and development initiatives, is seen as a key driver of employee productivity. In the oil and gas sector, workers who receive continuous training and development are better able to perform their jobs efficiently, making fewer mistakes and contributing to higher levels of output. As noted by Oladejo and Adeyemi (2021), productivity in the oil and gas sector can be significantly enhanced by the continuous development of

employees' technical skills, safety awareness, and problem-solving capabilities. A critical factor influencing employee productivity in the oil and gas industry is the work environment. According to Lee et al. (2019), the work environment, including factors such as safety, workplace culture, and management practices, plays a major role in determining employee performance. In high-risk industries such as oil and gas, ensuring that employees work in a safe and supportive environment is essential for maintaining productivity. The presence of clear communication, supportive leadership, and access to adequate resources and training can significantly reduce workplace stress and increase efficiency (Olajide, 2021). In contrast, a toxic work environment, characterised by poor management practices, lack of safety measures, or inadequate resources, can lead to decreased productivity, higher turnover rates, and more accidents. Employee engagement is another key factor that directly impacts productivity. Engaged employees are more likely to exhibit higher levels of productivity, as they are motivated to contribute to the success of the organisation. Saks (2006) defines employee engagement as the degree to which employees feel committed to their organisation and are motivated to perform their best work. In the oil and gas sector, where operational efficiency is critical, fostering a culture of engagement can lead to significant improvements in productivity. Engaged employees are not only more productive but also more likely to innovate and find solutions to problems that improve overall operations (Aguinis, 2019).

Human Relations Theory

Human Relations Theory (HRT) is a crucial framework in organisational behaviour that emerged as a response to the limitations of classical management theories. It emphasises the importance of social relationships, communication, employee well-being, and motivation in enhancing workplace productivity. The theory was primarily developed by Elton Mayo (1933) through the Hawthorne Studies, which revealed that worker productivity is significantly influenced by psychological and social factors rather than just economic incentives or mechanistic management approaches (Mayo, 1949). Prior to the advent of Human Relations Theory, classical management theories, such as Scientific Management by Frederick Taylor (1911) and Bureaucratic Management by Max Weber (1922), focused predominantly on efficiency, hierarchical structures, and rigid control mechanisms (Taylor, 1911; Weber, 1947). These theories regarded workers as mere cogs in a machine, assuming that financial rewards and strict supervision were the primary drivers of productivity. However, research in industrial psychology and sociology challenged these assumptions, leading to the rise of HRT as a more human-centred approach (Roethlisberger & Dickson, 1939). The Hawthorne Studies (1924–1932), conducted at Western Electric's Hawthorne Works in Chicago, provided empirical evidence that social interactions, group dynamics, and management style significantly impact worker performance (Mayo, 1933). The studies demonstrated that employees thrive in environments where they feel valued, heard, and part of a cohesive team. As a result, organisations began to shift their management strategies towards fostering employee engagement, job satisfaction, and participatory decision-making (Blumberg & Pringle, 1982). Human Relations Theory laid the foundation for modern organisational behaviour, influencing contemporary concepts such as employee motivation (Maslow, 1943), participative management (McGregor, 1960), and organisational culture (Schein, 1985). Today, HRT remains highly relevant in understanding workplace dynamics, leadership styles, and manpower development in various industries (Bolton & Houlihan, 2007). Given its emphasis on human interaction, the theory provides an essential framework for analysing the role of manpower development in improving productivity across selected industries in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Principles of Human Relations Theory

Human Relations Theory is based on several core principles that highlight the significance of interpersonal relationships, communication, and leadership in organisational success.

- i. **Social and Psychological Factors in Workplace Productivity:** One of the fundamental principles of HRT is that employees are not just motivated by economic incentives but also by social and psychological factors (Mayo, 1949). Workers perform better when they feel recognised, appreciated, and included in decision-making processes (Roethlisberger & Dickson, 1939). Mayo's studies found that informal social interactions and a supportive work environment play a crucial role in boosting employee morale and efficiency (Likert, 1961).
- ii. **Importance of Communication and Feedback:** HRT emphasises the role of communication in fostering positive workplace relationships. Effective two-way communication between employees and

management leads to better job satisfaction, reduced workplace conflicts, and increased organisational commitment (Barnard, 1938). Research has shown that companies with open communication policies tend to have higher employee engagement and lower turnover rates (Katz & Kahn, 1978).

- iii. **Employee Participation and Teamwork:** Another key tenet of HRT is the importance of participative management and teamwork. Unlike classical management theories that advocate for rigid hierarchies, HRT suggests that collaborative decision-making leads to better problem-solving and innovation (Argyris, 1957). Studies have demonstrated that organisations with democratic leadership structures tend to achieve higher employee productivity and organisational effectiveness (McGregor, 1960).
- iv. **Leadership and Motivation:** HRT highlights that leadership style has a direct impact on employee motivation and performance. Mayo's research revealed that leaders who adopt a people-oriented approach are more successful in maintaining workforce morale (Mayo, 1949). The theory influenced the development of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), which posits that workers require not just financial compensation but also recognition, belongingness, and self-actualisation for peak performance (Maslow, 1954).
- v. **Workplace Environment and Job Satisfaction:** HRT underscores that a positive workplace culture contributes significantly to job satisfaction and retention. Factors such as job security, work-life balance, and fair treatment are crucial for maintaining a motivated workforce (Herzberg, 1968). Research in industrial sociology has shown that organisations prioritising employee well-being experience lower absenteeism and greater productivity (Ouchi, 1981).

Application of Human Relations Theory to the Study

Human Relations Theory (HRT) provides a valuable lens through which to examine manpower development and productivity, particularly in the context of oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State. The theory highlights the significance of social dynamics, effective communication, employee engagement, and supportive leadership in enhancing workplace productivity—factors that are crucial in high-stakes and labor-intensive industries like oil and gas. In oil and gas firms, manpower development cannot be limited to technical training alone; it must also account for the psychological and social needs of employees. HRT underscores that productivity improves when workers feel valued, respected, and included in organisational processes. In this regard, implementing manpower development initiatives that incorporate mentorship, teamwork, and open feedback systems can significantly boost employee morale and motivation. Workers who believe their opinions matter and feel psychologically safe are more likely to engage meaningfully in training programs and apply acquired skills more effectively in their roles. The principle of effective communication, as emphasized in HRT, is especially critical in the oil and gas sector, where operations are often complex and hazardous. Ensuring two-way communication between management and employees can reduce misunderstandings, improve safety compliance, and foster a culture of trust. Feedback mechanisms, such as performance appraisals, suggestion boxes, and regular team meetings, can help identify skill gaps, assess training outcomes, and align manpower development strategies with operational goals. Furthermore, HRT's emphasis on leadership styles is relevant in developing human capital in oil and gas firms. Leaders who adopt a people-oriented approach—demonstrating empathy, fairness, and encouragement—are more likely to inspire loyalty and productivity among employees. This is particularly important in Bayelsa State, where local content policies and socio-political tensions require firms to balance technical efficiency with community engagement and staff inclusiveness.

Additionally, promoting participative management and teamwork, as advocated by HRT, enhances problem-solving and innovation. Encouraging employees at all levels to contribute ideas in areas such as safety, project execution, and resource management fosters a sense of ownership and accountability. This participatory culture strengthens internal cohesion, enhances job satisfaction, and reduces turnover—key factors that influence productivity. Lastly, a supportive work environment, as advocated by HRT, ensures that employees feel psychologically and emotionally stable. In an industry marked by high physical demands and long shifts, prioritising employee well-being through stress management programs, adequate rest periods, and fair treatment contributes significantly to improved performance. Therefore, applying

Human Relations Theory helps create a holistic manpower development strategy that boosts productivity in Bayelsa State’s oil and gas firms.

VI. Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-method research design, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively examine the relationship between manpower development programmes and employee productivity. The study was conducted in Bayelsa State and focused on selected oil and gas firms, namely SPDC, Conoil Producing Limited, and SEEPCO, with a total population of 3,000 employees. A sample size of 400 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula and selected through census and purposive sampling techniques. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, while secondary data were sourced from company records and reports. The research instruments were validated by experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach’s Alpha. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, Pearson’s correlation coefficient, and thematic analysis, all carried out using SPSS, with strict adherence to ethical research standards.

Table 1. Population Distribution of Staff in Selected Oil and Gas Firms in Bayelsa State

S/N	Company Name	Staff Strength	Source
1	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	1,500	SPDC Human Resource Department, Yenagoa Office, 2024
2	Conoil Producing Limited	900	Conoil HR Unit, Operations Base, Bayelsa State, 2024
3	Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO)	600	SEEPCO Administrative Office, Bayelsa Field Office, 2024
	Total	3000	

Table 2 Sample Size Distribution of Staff in Selected Oil and Gas Firms in Bayelsa State

S/N	Company Name	Company Name	Staff Population	Proportion (%)
1	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	1,500	50.0%
2	Conoil Producing Limited	Conoil Producing Limited	900	30.0%
3	Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO)	Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO)	600	20.0%
	Total	Total	3,000	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Company HR Records, 2024.

VII. Data Presentation

Table 3: Questionnaires Administered and Retrieved with Percentages

Questionnaire Status	Number	Percentage (%)
Administered	400	100.0
Retrieved	366	91.5
Not Retrieved	34	8.5
Total	400	100.0

Spss Output 2025

The data in Table 3 shows that a total of 400 questionnaires were administered, representing 100.0% of the study population. Out of this number, 366 were successfully retrieved, accounting for 91.5% of the total questionnaires distributed. Meanwhile, 34 questionnaires were not retrieved, representing 8.5% of the total administered. This high retrieval rate of 91.5% indicates a strong level of response and reliability for the study

Table 4.: Respondent Framework for Interviews

Position	Company	Location
Human Resource Manager	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	SPDC Bayelsa State Office
Training and Development Coordinator	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	SPDC Bayelsa State Office
Operations Manager	Conoil Producing Limited	Conoil Bayelsa State Office
HR Director	Conoil Producing Limited	Conoil Bayelsa State Office
Learning and Development Officer	Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO)	SEEPCO Bayelsa State Office
Senior HR Officer	Sterling Oil Exploration and Energy Production Company (SEEPCO)	SEEPCO Bayelsa State Office

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Company HR Records, 2025.

VIII. Data Analysis

Table 5: Answer to research question 1:What is the relationship between skills-job role alignment and organisational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State?

S/N	Items	SA F(%)	A F(%)	D F(%)	SD F(%)	Total	mean	Stand. D
6	My skills are well-matched to my job role, which enhances my productivity.	229(62.6%)	75(20.5%)	32(8.7%)	30(8.2%)	366	3.37	0.95
7	Proper alignment of employee skills to job roles improves overall organizational performance.	244(66.7%)	70(19.1%)	12(3.3%)	40(10.9%)	366	3.42	0.98
8	Employees perform better when their qualifications and job responsibilities align.	268(73.2%)	67(18.3%)	9(2.5%)	22(6%)	366	3.59	0.81
9	Misalignment between job roles and skills negatively affects company performance.	207(56.6%)	117(32%)	21(5.7%)	21(5.7%)	366	3.39	0.84
10	The organization assigns roles based on individual competencies and expertise.	222(60.7%)	80(21.9%)	33(9%)	31(8.5%)	366	3.35	0.96

Spss Output 2025

The data in Table 5 presents responses to research question 2 on the relationship between skills-job role alignment and organizational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State. For item 6, 229 respondents (62.6%) strongly agreed and 75 (20.5%) agreed that their skills were well-matched to their job roles, while 32 (8.7%) disagreed and 30 (8.2%) strongly disagreed, with a mean of 3.37 and a standard deviation of 0.95. In item 7, 244 respondents (66.7%) strongly agreed and 70 (19.1%) agreed that proper skills-job alignment improves overall organizational performance, compared to 12 (3.3%) who disagreed and 40 (10.9%) who strongly disagreed, resulting in a mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.98. Item 8 recorded the highest support, with 268 respondents (73.2%) strongly agreeing and 67 (18.3%) agreeing that employees perform better when qualifications align with job responsibilities, while only 9 (2.5%) disagreed and 22 (6.0%) strongly disagreed, yielding a mean of 3.59 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.81.

Similarly, in item 9, 207 respondents (56.6%) strongly agreed and 117 (32.0%) agreed that misalignment between job roles and skills negatively affects company performance, compared to 21 (5.7%) who disagreed and another 21 (5.7%) who strongly disagreed, giving a mean of 3.39 and standard deviation of 0.84. For item 10, 222 respondents (60.7%) strongly agreed and 80 (21.9%) agreed that roles are assigned based on competencies and expertise, while 33 (9.0%) disagreed and 31 (8.5%) strongly disagreed, producing a mean of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 0.96. Overall, in all five items, more than 80% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed, while less than 15% opposed. The mean scores, ranging between 3.35 and 3.59, show consistently high positive responses with low variability. These results clearly indicate that proper alignment of skills and job roles significantly enhances both employee productivity and organizational performance in the oil and gas firms surveyed.

Interview Responses to Research Question 1

Main Question: How does skills-job role alignment influence organisational performance?

Human Resource Manager, SPDC

*“In our company, we take skills-job alignment very seriously because mismatches often result in wasted time, low morale, and unnecessary errors. For instance, when engineers are assigned administrative duties outside their core technical expertise, productivity drops significantly. To prevent this, we ensure that job roles are strictly tied to an employee’s background, training, and proven capabilities. This approach has allowed us to reduce turnover, improve efficiency, and maximize employee potential. The performance metrics, such as project completion timelines and safety compliance, clearly show that alignment drives organizational performance.”

Training and Development Coordinator, SPDC

“I have observed that proper skills-job role alignment translates directly into measurable performance improvements. Employees who feel confident that their skills match their roles usually perform better and are more motivated. On the contrary, mismatched roles create frustration, errors, and delays. To address this, we run competency-based assessments and use the outcomes to guide role assignment and training priorities. This has significantly improved operational outcomes, with a noticeable increase in team productivity and the achievement of organizational targets.”

Operations Manager, Conoil Producing Limited

In operations, the consequences of misalignment are more visible and often costly. For example, when technical staff are not properly matched to the right equipment or processes, safety risks increase and efficiency suffers. We have therefore invested in systems that match employee competencies with job demands. Employees placed in roles aligned with their expertise perform tasks faster, with fewer mistakes, and with better innovation. This alignment has had a direct impact on the company’s overall performance, especially in terms of reduced downtime and cost savings.

Table 5: Answer to research question 2:How does soft skills development impact workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms?

S/N	Items	SA F(%)	A F(%)	D F(%)	SD F(%)	Total	mean	Stand. D
11	Developing soft skills such as communication and teamwork boosts employee efficiency.	233(63.7%)	70(19.1%)	41(11.2%)	22(6%)	366	3.40	0.91
12	Soft skills training encourages innovative thinking among staff.	195(53.3%)	128(35%)	21(5.7%)	22(6%)	366	3.36	0.84
13	Workplace collaboration improves significantly through soft skills development.	223(60.9%)	98(26.8%)	20(5.5%)	25(6.8%)	366	3.42	0.87
14	Employees with strong interpersonal skills contribute more to organizational innovation.	211(57.7%)	124(33.9%)	14(3.8%)	17(4.6%)	366	3.45	0.78
15	Soft skills development enhances problem-solving and adaptability in the workplace.	217(59.3%)	113(30.9%)	15(4.1%)	21(5.7%)	366	3.44	0.82

Spss Output 2025

The data in Table 5 addresses research question 2 on how soft skills development impacts workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms. For item 11, 233 respondents (63.7%) strongly agreed and 70 (19.1%) agreed that developing soft skills such as communication and teamwork boosts efficiency, while 41 (11.2%) disagreed and 22 (6.0%) strongly disagreed, giving a mean of 3.40 and standard deviation of 0.91. In item 12, 195 respondents (53.3%) strongly agreed and 128 (35.0%) agreed that soft skills training encourages innovative thinking, while 21 (5.7%) disagreed and 22 (6.0%) strongly disagreed, yielding a mean of 3.36 and standard deviation of 0.84. Item 13 shows that 223 respondents

(60.9%) strongly agreed and 98 (26.8%) agreed that workplace collaboration improves significantly through soft skills development, while 20 (5.5%) disagreed and 25 (6.8%) strongly disagreed, resulting in a mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.87. For item 14, 211 respondents (57.7%) strongly agreed and 124 (33.9%) agreed that employees with strong interpersonal skills contribute more to organizational innovation, compared to 14 (3.8%) who disagreed and 17 (4.6%) who strongly disagreed, producing a mean of 3.45 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.78. Similarly, item 15 revealed that 217 respondents (59.3%) strongly agreed and 113 (30.9%) agreed that soft skills development enhances problem-solving and adaptability, while 15 (4.1%) disagreed and 21 (5.7%) strongly disagreed, yielding a mean of 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.82. Overall, across all five items, more than 80% of respondents strongly agreed or agreed, while less than 12% opposed. The mean values, ranging from 3.36 to 3.45, indicate a consistently high level of agreement with relatively low variability. These results suggest that soft skills development plays a crucial role in boosting efficiency, enhancing collaboration, stimulating innovation, and strengthening problem-solving capacities within the oil and gas firms studied.

Interview Responses to Research Question 2

Main Question: How has soft skills development impacted workforce efficiency and innovation in your organization?

Human Resource Manager, SPDC

Soft skills training has greatly improved how our employees collaborate and communicate within teams. For example, after running structured communication workshops, we noticed a significant decline in misunderstandings and conflicts among staff. This has directly boosted efficiency because tasks are completed more smoothly and with fewer delays. Employees also show greater adaptability when unexpected challenges arise, which has improved problem-solving across departments. In my view, developing soft skills has been just as important as technical training in driving innovation in our company.

Training and Development Coordinator, SPDC

In our training programs, we focus on key soft skills like teamwork, negotiation, and leadership. These have been instrumental in encouraging innovative thinking among employees. Staff are now more willing to share ideas, challenge outdated practices, and collaborate on new solutions. This change has not only improved day-to-day efficiency but also helped us build a culture of innovation. It is very clear that when people have stronger interpersonal and communication skills, the organization benefits through better outcomes and higher performance levels.

IX. Test of Hypotheses

Table 6: H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between skills-job role alignment and organisational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State.

		Ho2 ind	Ho2 Dep
Ho2 ind	Pearson Correlation	1	.788**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	366	366
Ho2 Dep	Pearson Correlation	.788**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	366	366

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS output 2025

The correlation results in Table 6 show a strong positive relationship between skills-job role alignment (HO2 IND) and organizational performance (HO2 DEP), with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.788. This indicates that aligning employee skills with their job roles greatly enhances organizational performance. The significance value (Sig. 2-tailed) is 0.000, which is less than 0.01, confirming that the relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level. The analysis, based on 366 respondents, provides sufficient evidence to support the reliability of the findings. The results suggest that when employees' skills are properly matched with their job responsibilities, organizations in the oil and gas sector achieve higher levels of productivity and efficiency. This highlights the importance of effective human resource placement and competency-based role assignments.

Decision: Since $p = 0.000 < 0.01$, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected, confirming a significant relationship between skills-job role alignment and organizational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State

Table 7: H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between soft skills development and workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms.

		Correlations	
		Ho3 indep	Ho3 dep
Ho3 indep	Pearson Correlation	1	.756**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	366	366
Ho3 dep	Pearson Correlation	.756**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	366	366

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS output 2025

The correlation results in Table 7 indicate a strong positive relationship between soft skills development (HO3 indep) and workforce efficiency and innovation (HO3 dep), with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.756. This shows that improvements in soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving significantly enhance workforce efficiency and innovation in oil and gas firms. The significance value (Sig. 2-tailed) is 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 threshold, confirming that the relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level. With a sample size of 366 respondents, the findings are reliable and consistent. The results highlight that employees who develop strong interpersonal and adaptive skills contribute more effectively to innovation and overall performance. This underscores the importance of integrating soft skills training into manpower development strategies.

Decision: Since $p = 0.000 < 0.01$, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected, confirming a significant relationship between soft skills development and workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms.

X. Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between skills–job role alignment and organisational performance in the oil and gas sector of Bayelsa State?

The results presented in Table 4.8 provide strong evidence that aligning employee skills with job roles significantly enhances organisational performance in oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State. Across all five items, more than 80% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that skills–job role alignment leads to improved productivity, better performance, and greater organisational efficiency. For instance, 62.6% strongly agreed and 20.5% agreed that their skills were well-matched to their roles, with a mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of 0.95. Similarly, 66.7% strongly agreed and 19.1% agreed that proper skills–job alignment improves overall performance (mean = 3.42; SD = 0.98). The highest level of agreement was recorded in item 8, where 73.2% strongly agreed and 18.3% agreed that employees perform better when qualifications align with job responsibilities, giving a mean of 3.59 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.81. These findings demonstrate a strong consensus that skill alignment is a vital determinant of organisational performance. The correlation analysis further reinforces this conclusion. The test of hypothesis (H₀₂) revealed a significant positive relationship between skills–job role alignment and organisational performance, with a correlation coefficient of $r = .788$, $p < 0.01$. This high coefficient indicates that as the alignment between employee skills and job responsibilities improves, organisational

performance correspondingly increases. This finding validates the Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991), which emphasizes that organisations gain competitive advantage when they effectively utilize unique internal resources, such as employee expertise, that are difficult for competitors to imitate. In other words, by ensuring that the right people are in the right roles, oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State can optimise resource use and sustain performance. The interview responses provide additional support and context for these results. At SPDC, the Human Resource Manager emphasized that employees placed in roles matching their skills demonstrated higher productivity and fewer errors, while the Training and Development Coordinator highlighted that proper alignment reduces job stress and enhances motivation. At Conoil, the Operations Manager noted that mismatches between skills and job roles often led to inefficiencies and delays, whereas alignment promoted smooth workflow and innovation. The HR Director reinforced this point, stressing that assigning employees based on competencies had improved cross-departmental collaboration and organisational output. Similarly, at SEEPCO, both the Learning and Development Officer and Senior HR Officer observed that misalignment created frustration and reduced morale, while proper placement based on skillsets boosted efficiency and contributed to strategic goals. Collectively, these responses illustrate the practical impact of alignment on day-to-day operations and long-term organisational success. These findings are consistent with a growing body of empirical literature. For example, Okeke and Ugochukwu (2020) reported that proper skill-job alignment in Nigerian organisations was associated with reduced turnover, higher employee morale, and better productivity. Similarly, Ogunyomi and Ojikutu (2018) found that misalignment of skills and roles in oil firms often led to inefficiencies and operational setbacks, while strategic alignment enhanced innovation and profitability. International evidence also supports these conclusions. A study by Kristof-Brown, Zimmerman, and Johnson (2005) in the United States demonstrated that person–job fit strongly predicts job satisfaction, commitment, and performance outcomes. Likewise, Armstrong (2014) argued that organisations that align human resource planning with role specifications achieve greater efficiency, innovation, and competitiveness.

From a theoretical standpoint, the results align with Person–Job Fit Theory (Edwards, 1991), which posits that when there is congruence between an individual’s abilities and the demands of the job, higher levels of satisfaction and performance result. The strong positive responses to items 6–10 confirm that employees in Bayelsa’s oil and gas firms feel more effective when their qualifications and expertise align with their job roles. Additionally, the negative consequences of misalignment (as reflected in item 9, mean = 3.39, SD = 0.84) support the view that poor fit undermines both employee performance and overall organisational outcomes. This also ties to Expectancy Theory (Vroom, 1964), which suggests that employees exert more effort when they believe their skills are relevant to their roles and that their contributions will yield desired outcomes. Despite the overwhelmingly positive findings, the data also reveal areas of concern. Approximately 15–20% of respondents expressed disagreement across the items, indicating that skill-job role mismatches persist in some firms. For instance, 10.9% strongly disagreed that skill alignment improves organisational performance, and 14.2% disagreed or strongly disagreed that roles are assigned based on competencies. This minority view highlights structural or managerial gaps in workforce planning, which may hinder the full benefits of manpower development. As Onyema (2018) observed, Nigerian organisations often fail to adequately match training outcomes with job placements, resulting in underutilisation of employee competencies. Similarly, Adeniji (2017) noted that skill-job mismatches contribute to employee dissatisfaction and reduced productivity, particularly in industries with rapidly changing technological requirements. The mean values (ranging between 3.35 and 3.59) and standard deviations (0.81–0.98) suggest a strong consensus but also indicate variability in perceptions. This variability may reflect differences in organisational policies, effectiveness of HR practices, or individual experiences across the surveyed firms. The interviews help explain this variation: while some firms like SPDC and SEEPCO had robust systems for aligning employees with roles, others struggled with inconsistent practices. This underlines the need for standardised, competency-based approaches to workforce planning across the industry.

In summary, the findings from research question two underscore the critical role of skills-job role alignment in enhancing organisational performance. The statistical evidence, qualitative insights, and supporting literature converge to show that employees perform better, experience higher satisfaction, and contribute more meaningfully to organisational outcomes when their skills match their job roles. Conversely, misalignment leads to inefficiencies, frustration, and reduced organisational performance. The

results validate theoretical models such as Person–Job Fit Theory, Resource-Based View, and Expectancy Theory, while also highlighting the practical implications for HR managers in the oil and gas sector. To maximise performance, firms must invest in accurate job analysis, competency mapping, and continuous review of employee placement strategies.

Research Question 2: How does soft skills development impact workforce efficiency and innovation in selected oil and gas firms?

The results presented in Table 4.9 show that soft skills development has a strong and positive impact on workforce efficiency and innovation in Bayelsa State’s oil and gas firms. Across all five items, the majority of respondents strongly agreed or agreed that communication, teamwork, collaboration, interpersonal skills, and adaptability significantly enhance both efficiency and innovation. For instance, 63.7% strongly agreed and 19.1% agreed that developing soft skills such as communication and teamwork boosts efficiency, while only 17.2% disagreed or strongly disagreed (mean = 3.40; SD = 0.91). Similarly, 53.3% strongly agreed and 35.0% agreed that soft skills training encourages innovative thinking, with only 11.7% opposed (mean = 3.36; SD = 0.84). These consistently high levels of agreement reflect widespread recognition of the importance of soft skills in fostering collaboration and creativity within the sector. Further, items 13–15 highlight the broader organisational benefits of soft skills. For example, 60.9% strongly agreed and 26.8% agreed that workplace collaboration improves significantly through soft skills development (mean = 3.42; SD = 0.87). Likewise, 57.7% strongly agreed and 33.9% agreed that employees with strong interpersonal skills contribute more to organisational innovation, producing the highest mean of 3.45 and the lowest standard deviation of 0.78, indicating strong consensus. Finally, 59.3% strongly agreed and 30.9% agreed that soft skills development enhances problem-solving and adaptability (mean = 3.44; SD = 0.82). Together, these results suggest that soft skills are not merely complementary but are essential for maintaining organisational efficiency, innovation, and resilience in a rapidly changing industry.

The correlation analysis (H03) reinforces these results, showing a significant positive relationship between soft skills development and workforce efficiency/innovation, with a coefficient of $r = .756$, $p < 0.01$. This strong correlation highlights that as soft skills training increases, employees become more efficient and more innovative. This finding validates Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964), which asserts that investments in employees’ knowledge and competencies—including non-technical skills—yield productivity and innovation benefits. It also reflects the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece, Pisano & Shuen, 1997), which emphasizes that organisations thrive in competitive environments when they cultivate flexible, adaptive skills that enable innovation and change. The interview responses provide rich qualitative evidence supporting the survey results. At SPDC, the Human Resource Manager observed that communication workshops reduced conflicts and misunderstandings, thereby boosting efficiency. The Training and Development Coordinator further explained that teamwork and leadership programmes encouraged employees to share ideas, challenge outdated practices, and innovate collaboratively. At Conoil, the Operations Manager highlighted the impact of soft skills on safety and coordination, noting that improved communication reduced operational errors, while the HR Director explained how interpersonal skills strengthened cross-functional projects and brainstorming sessions, leading to practical innovations. Similarly, at SEEPCO, the Learning and Development Officer emphasized that soft skills training enhanced adaptability and proactive problem-solving, while the Senior HR Officer noted that teamwork and emotional intelligence training reduced conflicts and improved innovation. These real-world perspectives confirm that soft skills development is deeply integrated into daily operations and is critical for sustaining innovation. The findings resonate strongly with existing empirical literature. For example, Onyema (2018) found that soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and adaptability were key drivers of innovation and collaboration in Nigeria’s oil sector. Similarly, Iheriohanma (2017) emphasized that while technical expertise is essential, non-technical competencies often determine how effectively employees apply their skills in dynamic workplace contexts. International studies also reinforce these conclusions. Robles (2012) argued that soft skills are as important as technical skills for organisational success, while Gibb (2014) highlighted their role in fostering innovation, adaptability, and resilience in volatile industries. These studies align with the present findings, which show that soft skills development boosts both efficiency and innovation in Bayelsa’s oil and gas firms.

From a theoretical perspective, the results strongly support the Human Capital Theory and Dynamic Capabilities Theory. Human Capital Theory highlights the productivity gains from skill development, while Dynamic Capabilities Theory underscores the need for organisations to cultivate flexible and adaptive skills to sustain innovation. Furthermore, the findings can also be interpreted through the lens of Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964): when organisations invest in soft skills training, employees reciprocate by contributing to efficiency and innovation, thereby strengthening organisational performance. Nevertheless, the data also indicate challenges. Between 10–17% of respondents expressed disagreement across items, suggesting that not all employees experience direct benefits from soft skills programmes. For instance, 11.2% disagreed and 6.0% strongly disagreed that communication and teamwork improved efficiency, while 11.7% opposed the view that soft skills training encouraged innovation. These minority responses may reflect differences in training quality, delivery methods, or organisational culture. As Adeniji (2017) noted, many Nigerian firms treat soft skills training as peripheral, offering generic workshops that fail to translate into practical workplace improvements. This underscores the need for firms to design more context-specific, outcome-oriented programmes that integrate soft skills into technical and operational training. The mean values (3.36–3.45) and relatively low standard deviations (0.78–0.91) show both strong agreement and consistency in responses, though the slightly lower mean for innovation (3.36) suggests that while employees recognise improvements, the link between soft skills and innovation may require further strengthening. This observation aligns with findings by Okwuonu (2020), who argued that while soft skills improve collaboration, their impact on innovation is maximised only when supported by an organisational culture that encourages risk-taking and experimentation. In summary, the findings from research question three reveal that soft skills development plays a critical role in enhancing workforce efficiency, fostering collaboration, and stimulating innovation in oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State. Both the quantitative and qualitative results demonstrate that training in communication, teamwork, adaptability, and interpersonal skills leads to more efficient operations, reduced conflicts, stronger problem-solving, and greater innovative output. Supported by Human Capital Theory, Dynamic Capabilities Theory, and Social Exchange Theory, as well as empirical literature, these findings confirm that soft skills are indispensable for organisational success in dynamic and competitive industries. However, to maximise their impact, firms must ensure that soft skills training is practical, context-specific, and integrated into broader manpower development strategies.

XI. Key Findings

1. Skills-job role alignment significantly enhances organisational productivity.
2. Soft skills development improves workforce efficiency and innovation.

XII. Conclusion

The study concluded that manpower development significantly enhances organisational performance, workforce efficiency, and innovation in selected oil and gas firms in Bayelsa State. The findings revealed that effective alignment between employees' skills and job roles leads to higher productivity, improved operational efficiency, reduced errors, greater employee satisfaction, and enhanced organisational outcomes. Similarly, the study established that soft skills development, including communication, teamwork, adaptability, and interpersonal competencies, contributes substantially to workforce efficiency, collaboration, problem-solving, and innovation. The statistical analyses confirmed strong positive and significant relationships between skills–job role alignment and organisational performance, as well as between soft skills development and workforce efficiency and innovation. The interview findings further reinforced these results by demonstrating that employees perform optimally when their competencies match job requirements and when organisations invest in relevant soft skills training. The study therefore concluded that manpower development remains a strategic tool for achieving sustainable organisational success, competitiveness, innovation, and improved employee performance in the oil and gas sector. Consequently, organisations should prioritize competency-based workforce planning, continuous skills development, and effective employee placement strategies to maximize productivity and organisational effectiveness.

XIII. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Organisations should implement structured skills-job role alignment policies to reduce inefficiencies.
2. Firms must integrate soft skills development as a core part of training to improve innovation and efficiency.

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